

Synthesis, characterization, electrochemical properties and antibacterial activity of some transition metal complexes with 2-[N-(2'-hydroxy-1'-naphthylidene)-amino]-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene

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Abstract : A potentially tridentate Schiff base has been prepared by condensing 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde under well defined condition. The ligand is versatile in forming a series of metal complexes with transition metal ions such as manganese(II), iron(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II). The ligand and the metal complexes have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance values, magnetic susceptibility data, NMR, UV-Visible, IR and EPR spectral studies wherever possible and applicable. The spectral studies reveal that the Schiff base behaves as monobasic tridentate, coordinating to the metal ion through azomethine nitrogen, ester carbonyl oxygen and the naphtholate oxygen after deprotonation. Analytical data reveal that nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes possess 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratios while manganese(II), iron(II) and cobalt(II) complexes exhibit 1 : 2 ratios. Molar conductance values support the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The electrochemical behaviour of the copper(II) complex has been investigated by cyclic voltammetry. The ligand and the metal complexes have been subjected to antibacterial studies and it has been observed that the complexes are more potent bactericides than the ligands.

Keywords : Schiff base, molar conductance, cyclic voltammetry, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Schiff bases play a very important role in the field of coordination chemistry of transition, inner-transition and main group elements¹⁻⁵. Among the prodigious number and variety of Schiff base complexes those derived from salicylaldehydes form the major part mainly because of their synthetic proclivity and structural diversities. However, metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 2-aminothiophene derivative have received comparatively less attention. This is mainly because of the instability of 2-aminothiophene. But in this investigation, 2-aminothiophene has been made stable by suitable substitution at the remaining positions of the thiophene ring by an ester group and two methyl groups. The resulting compound namely 2-amino-3-

carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene has been condensed with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde to form a potentially tridentate Schiff base viz. 2-[N-(2'-hydroxy-1'-naphthylidene)amino]-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene. Apart from this, Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are of special interest because; some of them have been known to show photochromism and thermochromism in the solid state⁶. One of the reasons for photochromism is an intramolecular proton transfer associated with a change in the π -electron configuration. The presence of hydroxy group near the site of coordination has been regarded as one of the requirements, which accounts for the formation of either phenolimine or quinoneamine tautomeric forms. Recently, liquid crystal researchers have also made a significant

revelation that the introduction of lateral polar hydroxy group will enhance the molecular polarizability and stabilize the liquid crystalline compounds⁷. In this paper, we describe the synthesis, characterization, cyclic voltammetric and antibacterial studies on some 3*d*-metal complexes with the above mentioned Schiff base.

Results and discussion

Formation of metal complexes can be represented by the following general equation.

The complexes obtained are presented in Table 1. All the complexes are stable at room temperature and possess

Structure of the ligand and metal complexes :

Analytical data indicated that the condensation of 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde occurred in 1 : 1 ratio to form a heterocyclic Schiff base ligand, 2-[*N*-(2'-hydroxy-1'-naphthylidene)amino]-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene, which has been characterized through various spectral data.

UV-Visible spectra :

Antonov and co-workers examined the structure of Schiff base derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde based on UV-Visible spectra and suggested the existence of phenolimine-quinoneimine tautomeric forms in such Schiff bases and characteristic bands have been assigned for these tautomers⁹ (Fig. 1a and b). This phenomenon of tautomerism depends on several factors like nature of the

Table 1. Analytical data and other details of the bivalent metal complexes

Complex	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) :					Molar conductance ^a ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		Found (Calcd.)					
		M	C	H	N	S	
[Mn(NAT) ₂]	Light brown	7.51 (7.24)	63.67 (63.25)	4.39 (4.74)	3.36 (3.69)	8.13 (8.43)	10.2
[Fe(NAT) ₂]	Light orange	7.09 (7.35)	63.57 (63.17)	4.36 (4.74)	3.87 (3.68)	8.16 (8.42)	8.8
[Co(NAT) ₂]	Dark brown	7.49 (7.72)	62.67 (62.92)	4.43 (4.72)	3.30 (3.67)	8.05 (8.39)	9.1
[Ni(NAT)Cl]	Yellowish orange	13.37 (13.16)	53.48 (53.79)	4.24 (4.03)	3.38 (3.14)	7.46 (7.17)	6.4
[Cu(NAT)Cl]	Orange brown	14.27 (14.09)	53.47 (53.22)	3.67 (3.99)	3.43 (3.10)	7.35 (7.09)	7.3
[Zn(NAT)Cl]	Brown	14.19 (14.44)	53.43 (53.00)	3.61 (3.97)	3.37 (3.09)	7.43 (7.07)	8.5

^aMeasured in DMSO.

good keeping qualities. They are non-hygroscopic solids soluble in organic solvents. Formulation of these complexes has been done on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements. Molar conductance values of the complexes in DMSO ($10^{-3} M$) solution adequately confirm the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes⁸. Manganese(II), iron(II) and cobalt(II) complexes exhibit 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio while the others viz. nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) possess 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio.

solvent, nature of the substituent, temperature etc. But in the present case, the ligand exhibited a high energy absorption band at 278 and 323 nm ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$) which corresponds to phenolimine form of the ligand in the solid state.

The ultraviolet spectra of all the metal chelates reveal that a high energy absorption band at 278 and 323 nm of the ligand is shifted only marginally in metal complexes indicating the existence of phenolimine form of the ligand in the metal complexes also.

Fig. 1. Tautomeric forms of the HNAT ligand.

Infrared spectra :

In agreement with the UV spectrum, infrared spectrum of the ligand exhibited a broad band ranging from 3300–3100 cm^{-1} and centered at 3175 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to the hydrogen bonded phenolic -OH group. An intense band at 1700 cm^{-1} is assignable to the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group of the ester carbonyl function and another medium intensity band appearing at 1621 cm^{-1} and also a band at 1291 cm^{-1} can be assignable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the azomethine group and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ of the naphtholate oxygen respectively. In addition to these bands the substituted thiophene ring vibrations¹⁰ have been observed at 1525, 1420 and 1355 cm^{-1} . All these spectral evidences are in good accord

with an enolimine structure of the ligand. It has also been observed that the ester carbonyl, azomethine nitrogen and phenolic -OH are involved in a sort of bifunctional hydrogen bonding¹¹.

Infrared spectra of the metal complexes are closely similar among themselves. The infrared spectra of the complexes and the ligands have been compared very carefully to determine the donor functions of the ligand involved in bonding with metal ions. Only those bands diagnostic of coordination are considered and are presented in Table 2. The infrared spectral bands of the are very close to each other and the spectral data correspond to the structure obtained by the replacement of the

Table 2. Infrared and far infrared spectral data (cm^{-1}) of the ligand and its bivalent metal complexes

HNAT	[Mn(NAT) ₂]	[Fe(NAT) ₂]	[Co(NAT) ₂]	[Ni(NAT)Cl]	[Cu(NAT)Cl]	[Zn(NAT)Cl]	Tentative assignments
3300-3100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Hydrogen bonded $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$
1700	1662	1661	1663	1660	1664	1665	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$
1621	1591	1592	1594	1591	1596	1593	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$
1525	1523	1527	1524	1526	1528	1522	Substituted thiophene ring
1420	1418	1423	1422	1419	1421	1422	„
1355	1352	1356	1358	1356	1355	1353	„
1291	1326	1328	1321	1330	1327	1329	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$
-	548	545	547	542	546	550	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$
-	444	442	448	446	450	445	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
-	-	-	-	358	360	355	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$

hydrogen bonded hydrogen atom of the ligand by metal ion. In the metal chelates, the characteristic frequencies of the ligand due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ are perturbed indicating their involvement in coordination. The broad band ranging from $3300\text{--}3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and centered at 3175 cm^{-1} is cleared from this region. It is an obvious indication of deprotonation of the phenolic $-\text{OH}$ and coordination of oxygen atom to the metal ion. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ observed in the ligand at 1291 cm^{-1} is shifted to higher frequency by $\sim 35\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes revealing coordination by the oxygen atom of the deprotonated phenolic $-\text{OH}$. The ester carbonyl stretching frequency is decreased by $35\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the azomethine frequency is lowered by $25\text{--}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the involvement of these groups in coordination. However, the vibrations characteristic of thiophene ring system remain almost unaffected^{10,12,13}. This is a clear indication of the non-involvement of ring sulphur in bond formation.

Further evidence of bonding by nitrogen and oxygen atoms has been provided by far infrared spectra of the complexes. Far infrared spectra of the complexes showed several non-ligand bands in the relevant region. Due to the interference of skeletal vibrations of the ligands with $\text{M}-\text{O}$ and $\text{M}-\text{N}$ vibrations, definite assignments of bands due to metal-ligand vibration has been rendered difficult. Therefore tentative assignments have been made by comparing the spectra of the complexes with those of the free ligand. Regions at $550\text{--}542$, $450\text{--}442$ and $360\text{--}355\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been observed for $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ vibrations respectively^{14,15}. Thus it is clear from above spectral data that the ligand acted as monobasic tridentate, bonding through the azomethine nitrogen, deprotonated phenolate oxygen and ester carbonyl oxygen.

¹H NMR spectra :

Conclusive evidence for the phenylimine structure of the ligand was provided by the proton NMR spectrum in CDCl_3 which shows peaks at $\delta 9.1$ and 14.1 assignable to azomethine proton and hydrogen bonded phenolic $-\text{OH}$ respectively¹⁶. The absence of peak at $\delta 13.71$ due to $-\text{NH}$ proton ruled out the existence of quinoneimine form of the ligand. Signals for methyl protons and methylene protons of the ester function were observed at $\delta 1.2$ and

3.7 , respectively and the aromatic proton signals were observed in the range of $\delta 6.8\text{--}8.1$ (Fig. 2). All these observations give sufficient support to the conclusion drawn on the basis of UV and IR spectral data.

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of the HNAT ligand.

The ¹H NMR spectra of nickel(II) and zinc(II) complexes have been recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$. The $-\text{OH}$ proton signal of the ligand disappeared in the metal chelates. This is a clear evidence of the coordination of the phenolic $-\text{OH}$ to the metal ion through the deprotonated enolate oxygen. The signals of methyl, methylene and aromatic protons show slight change in comparison with those of the ligand. Based on the above spectral data, the following structures (Figs. 3 and 4) have been assigned for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes.

Fig. 3. Structure of 1 : 1 metal complex.

Fig. 4. Structure of 1 : 2 metal complex.

Electronic spectral data and magnetic moment values :

The magnetic moment value of manganese(II) complex indicates a high-spin octahedral environment around the metal ion. Electronic spectra of this complex showed weak absorption bands around 14150, 16600 and 19380 cm^{-1} which are compatible with distorted octahedral geometry around metal ion¹⁷. Spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\text{NAT})_2]$ gave a weak absorption band centered at 11170 cm^{-1} , which is due to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ transition and is characteristic of a high-spin octahedral geometry¹⁸ around iron(II). Cobalt(II) complex exhibited bands at 7240, 17350 and 20370 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively (Table 3). Tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes have generally lower mag-

netic moment values of the range 4.20–4.58 B.M. But the magnetic moment values for the corresponding octahedral complexes are around 4.8 B.M. and also the observed electronic spectral data for the present cobalt(II) complexes are comparable with an octahedral geometry around the metal ion¹⁹. The electronic spectrum of nickel(II) complex exhibited two bands around at 13400 and 18950 cm^{-1} which are assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions respectively. These transitions along with the diamagnetic nature of the complex suggest a square planar geometry for the nickel(II) complex²⁰. The completely filled *d*-orbitals in zinc(II) and the absence of LFSE seem largely responsible for the much less extensive coordination chemistry of zinc(II). The zinc(II) ion is flexible with respect to the number of ligands it can adopt in its coordination shell. Analytical data and conductance values of zinc(II) complexes adequately support their formation as in Table 1. The three coordinating sites are occupied by the donor atoms of the ligand and the remaining coordinating site is occupied by the chloride ion. Hence a coordination number of four is preferred. It has been reported that tetrahedral geometry²¹ is the most preferred structure for four coordinated zinc(II).

EPR spectra :

The X-band EPR spectra of the copper(II) complex was recorded in the solid state at room temperature and also in DMSO at liquid nitrogen temperature using TCNE free radical as the 'g' marker. The complex has well resolved g_{\parallel} and a broad g_{\perp} regions and various Hamiltonian parameters have been calculated ($g_{\parallel} = 2.242$, $g_{\perp} = 2.043$, $A_{\parallel} = 165$). The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ indicates that the unpaired electron is most likely in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital²². The covalency parameter (α^2) has been calculated using Kivelson and Neiman equation²³. The covalency parameter (α^2) indicates considerable covalent character of the metal-ligand bond²⁴.

Cyclic voltammetry :

Electrochemical behaviour of the free ligand and its $[\text{Cu}(\text{NAT})\text{Cl}]$ complex (Fig. 5) were examined by using glassy carbon as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and platinum wire as auxiliary electrode. The working media consisted of DMSO and Bu_4NClO_4 as supporting electrolyte. The solution was degassed with argon prior to use and kept under an argon atmosphere. A solution of 2 mM was used at room temperature in the potential range -2.0 to $+2.0$ with a scan rate 50 and 100 mV/s.

Table 3. Electronic spectral data and magnetic moment values of the metal complexes

Complex	Absorption bands	Tentative assignments (cm^{-1})	Magnetic moment (B.M.)
[Mn(NAT) ₂]	14150	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$	5.80
	16600	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$	
	19380	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g, {}^4A_{1g}$	
[Fe(NAT) ₂]	11170	${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$	5.26
[Co(NAT) ₂]	7240	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$	4.82
	17350	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$	
	20370	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$	
[Ni(NAT)Cl]	13400	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$	Diamagnetic
	18950	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$	
[Cu(NAT)Cl]	13920	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$	1.81

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammogram of the copper(II) complex.

The CV profile has displayed waves at E_{pa} at -0.500 V and E_{pc} at -1.0217 V and a second wave at E_{pa} $+0.1028$ and E_{pc} $+0.04173$ V respectively. The former is due to the reversible reaction of the ligand, since such observations have also been seen in the free ligand and the latter is due to reversible reaction of the complex. The number of electron transfer for the reversible couple is determined from the peak separation. Also, the rate of peak current approaches to one, supports a single electron transfer mechanism in the complex. Thus from the voltammetric data, the electrochemical process is $[Cu^{II}(NAT)Cl] + 1e \rightarrow [Cu^{I}(NAT)Cl]$. Here also the reaction is diffusion controlled and decomplexation was not observed²⁵.

Formulation of the complexes has been made on the basis of their analytical data, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility measurements and various spectral data. It was found that the composition of the complexes varied with the nature of the metal ion. Thus nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) formed 1 : 1 complexes while manganese(II), iron(II) and cobalt(II) complexes exhibited 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratios.

Antibacterial activity :

Most of the micro-organisms acquire resistance to

common antibiotics. Retention of potency of antibiotic drugs will be highly desirable in clinical treatments. Metal complexes especially transition metal complexes are found fatal to micro-organisms but not to the host in micro quantities. Allured by these observations, the ligand and the metal complexes have been tested for their antibacterial activity by a reported method²⁶ and the results obtained are presented in Table 4 and Fig. 6. It has been observed that all the metal complexes are more potent bactericides than the ligand. This enhancement in the activity can be explained on the basis of chelation theory²⁷.

Table 4. Antibacterial study of the ligand and its metal complexes

Ligand/ Complex	Zone of inhibition (mm)		
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>V. cholerae</i>	<i>B. megaterium</i>
HNAT	16	17	16
[Mn(NAT) ₂]	20	20	22
[Fe(NAT) ₂]	24	22	25
[Co(NAT) ₂]	25	22	24
[Ni(NAT)Cl]	22	21	25
[Cu(NAT)Cl]	26	24	28
[Zn(NAT)Cl]	22	23	26
Standard	28	27	30

Fig. 6. Antibacteriogram of the HNAT ligand and its metal complexes.

Chelation reduces the polarity of the metal ion considerably mainly because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and possible π -electron delocalization over the whole chelate ring. The reduced polarity of the metal ion in turn increases its lipophilic character. This favours interaction with lipids and polysaccharides which are important constituents of cell wall and membrane. The cells also contain many amino phosphates,

carbonyl and cysteinyl ligands which maintain the integrity of the membrane by acting as diffusion barrier and also provide suitable sites for binding. These cell components may also be preferred for metal ion interaction. The higher toxicity of the metal complexes can be attributed to the effect of metal ion on the normal cell processes²⁸. The increased interaction of the metal ion with lipid molecules of the cell, most probably leads to the breakdown of permeability barrier of the cell resulting in interference with the normal cell processes. However, chelation is not the only criterion for antimicrobial activity but factors such as nature of the metal ion, nature of ligand, coordinating sites, geometry of the complex, concentration, hydrophilicity, lipophilicity, presence of other co-ligands, steric and pharmacokinetic factors also play important roles in deciding the potency of the antimicrobial agent²⁹. The cells contain a variety of functional groups that can act as metal-binding sites, but at the same time the non-polar cell membranes hinder the movement of charged metal ions into the cell, where a myriad of metal-binding sites exist to compete for the metal ion. Hence, the interaction of metal ions with cellular compounds is hindered to a certain extent. In order to achieve better metal ion-cell interaction, the complex should possess sufficient lipid solubility to permit transport of the metal across the cell membranes and it must have high thermodynamic stability to reach the site without being dissociated. Finally, it can act as metal complex with cells to produce a selective effect in order to obtain therapeutic value³⁰.

Experimental

Physical measurements :

The metal content of the complexes were determined by using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Nulab GBC 902). Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were performed using Elementar Systeme, Vario EL III CHN analyzer. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Varian Cary 5000 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Thermo-Nicolet Avatar 370 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Proton NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ on a JEOL GSX 400 MHz FT NMR spectrometer. Far IR spectra were recorded on a Polytec FIR 30 Fourier Far IR spectrophotometer using CsI discs. Molar conductance mea-

surements in DMSO were made at room temperature using a Systronic Model 304 digital conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility values of the complexes were measured at room temperature with a Gouy type magnetic balance. The EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded in the solid state and also in DMSO at the temperature of liquid nitrogen using a Varian-112 EPR spectrometer and cyclic voltammetric study of the copper(II) complex was performed on a BAS CV-50 analyzer.

Synthesis of 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene :

2-Amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene, the starting material for the synthesis of the heterocyclic Schiff base was prepared by a reported method³¹.

Synthesis of 2-[N-(2'-hydroxy-1'-naphthylidene)amino]-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-diethylthiophene :

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (0.01 mol) dissolved in EtOH (40 mL), was added gradually to an ethanolic solution (30 mL) of 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5-dimethylthiophene (0.01 mol). One drop of piperidine was added as condensating agent and refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The volume of the solution was reduced to half of the initial volume and allowed to crystallize. The crystals collected were further purified by recrystallization from EtOH and dried in vacuum over P₂O₅. Yield 80%.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

To a magnetically stirred solution of the ligand (0.01 mol) in EtOH (40 mL) an ethanolic solution of the metal salt (0.005 mol, 20 mL) was added in the appropriate ratio. The pH of the solution was maintained between 6–7 and refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. The solution was concentrated and allowed to cool. The complex that separated was filtered off, washed with EtOH and dried in vacuum. Yield 78–83%.

Antibacterial studies :

The ligand and the metal complexes were screened for their antibacterial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus megaterium* and *Vibrio cholerae* at a concentration of 200 µg ml⁻¹ in DMSO using the agar diffusion method^{26,32}.

A hot nutrient agar solution (20 mL) was poured into sterilized petri dishes and allowed to attain room temperature (agar plates). The seed layer medium was melted

and then cooled to about 45 °C with gentle shaking. The previously grown subculture was added to the seed layer medium aseptically and mixed well. It was immediately lawned into the petri dishes and allowed to attain room temperature. Filter paper discs of 5 mm diameter soaked with the test solution were placed on the petri dishes and allowed to cool for an hour to facilitate diffusion. The plates were then incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. At the end of incubation period, the zone of inhibition around the filter paper discs were measured in mm. Streptomycin was used as the standard antibacterial agent.

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References

1. A. S. Ahmed and L. Wolfgang, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 2007, **138**, 175.
2. C. Bazzicalupi, A. Bencini, A. Bianchi, A. Danesi, E. Faggi, C. Giorgi, S. Santarelli and B. Valtancoli, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **252**, 1052.
3. J. Joseph and B. H. Mehta, *Russian Journal of Coord. Chem.*, 2007, **33**, 124.
4. K. C. Gupta and A. K. Sutar, *Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part A : Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 2007, **44**, 1171.
5. Y. Sindhu, C. J. Athira, M. S. Sujamol and K. Mohanan, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2010, **185**, 1955.
6. M. Yddiz, H. Unver, D. Erdener, N. Ocak, A. Erdonmez and T. N. Durlu, *Cryst. Res. Technol.*, 2006, **41**, 600.
7. N. V. S. Rao, D. Singha, M. Das and M. K. Paul, *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 2002, **373**, 105.
8. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
9. L. Antonov, W. M. F. Fabian, D. Nedeltcheva and F. S. Kamounah, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 2000, **2**, 1173.
10. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1963.
11. K. Mohanan, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 2004, **20**, 331.
12. A. Angoso, L. J. M. Martin, J. L. Manzano, M. Martin, R. Martin, E. Rodriguez and J. Soria, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1992, **195**, 45.
13. S. Gronowitz, A. R. Katritzky and R. E. Reavill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3881.
14. K. Mohanan and B. Murukan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Nano Met. Chem.*, 2005, **35**, 837.
15. L. Chen, L. K. Thompson and J. N. Bridson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1993, **32**, 2938.
16. S. Sitram, D. Fregona and G. Faraglia, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1988, **18**, 269.
17. R. K. Parihari, R. K. Patel and R. N. Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 339.
18. D. N. Sathyanarayana, "Electronic Absorption Spectroscopy and Related Techniques", University Press Limited, Hyderabad, 2001.
19. K. N. Thimmaiah, W. D. Lloyd and G. T. Chandrappa, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **106**, 81.
20. N. Raman, V. Muthuraj, S. Ravichandran and A. Kulandaisamy, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 2003, **115**, 161.
21. D. Todor and L. Carmay, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 11146.
22. B. Singh, B. P. Yadav and R. C. Agarwal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 441.
23. D. Kivelson and R. Neiman, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149.
24. S. N. Shetti, A. S. R. Murty and G. L. Tembe, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 318.
25. A. J. Bard and L. R. Faulkner, "Electrochemical Methods", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1980.
26. T. R. Johnson and C. L. Case, "Laboratory Experiments in Microbiology", Benjamin Cummings, Wesley Longman, Sanfrancisco, 2001.
27. B. G. Tweedy, *Phytopathology*, 1964, **55**, 910.
28. B. Singh, R. N. Singh and R. C. Agarwal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 1016.
29. B. Oliva, A. O'Neill, J. M. Wilson, P. J. O'Hanton and I. Chopra, *Antibac. Agent Chemother.*, 2001, **45**, 532.
30. D. H. Petering, "Inorganic and Nutritional Aspects of Cancer", ed. G. N. Schrauzer, Plenum Press, New York, 1978, pp.179-191.
31. K. Gewald, E. Schinke and H. Botcher, *Chem. Ber.*, 1966, **99**, 94.
32. J. G. Collee, J. P. Duguid, A. G. Farser and B. D. Marmion (eds.), "Practical Medical Microbiology", Churchill Livingstone, New York, 1989.